

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

Deliverable 3.1

Landscaping procedure guidelines

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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CONTENTS

CONTENTS.....	2
Summary.....	3
1. Introduction.....	3
2. Landscaping procedure guidelines:.....	3
Prioritization of needs; Stakeholder consultation.....	3
Identification of relevant RIs.....	4
3. Development of vision and Landscaping.....	5
4. Final Remarks.....	5
Appendix.....	6
Acronyms.....	6
Outline of Questionnaire.....	6

Summary

The present document provides the guidelines for the landscaping procedure needed to provide a cross-thematic landscape of actual available services. The landscaping exercise has a key role providing a solid background for the activities of other work packages of the project (WP4-WP8), aiming at understanding the current scientific needs, identifying the “thematic priorities” as well as service gaps and the strategy for the technology development.

1. Introduction

Landscaping Research Infrastructures (RIs) play a pivotal role in evaluating and monitoring RIs about their capacity and capability and help shape the future of scientific inquiry and innovation. The main goal of this project is to set the framework for providing the European scientific community with easily accessible services to study and analyze the impact of artificial materials on life, both directly and indirectly, via a One Health approach, on health, food, and the environment. A comprehensive strategic plan delineating goals, objectives, and actions is thus essential for this endeavor. By aligning with the needs and priorities of the research community, organizations, and stakeholders, our effort aims to provide a comprehensive landscape of RIs, and accelerate scientific discovery by targeting the development of RIs, and support of state-of-the-art approaches, to address our objective. Thus, understanding the current RIs’ landscape and identifying priorities and opportunities for improvement can not only optimize existing resources but, importantly, support the long-term development of RIs. As an initial step, a comprehensive assessment of RIs is essential for understanding their status and identifying gaps that targeted funding can address. Such efforts will also contribute to the enhanced impact of ESFRI, fostering its own growth and sustainability.

2. Landscaping procedure guidelines:

Prioritization of needs; Stakeholder consultation

- The initial prioritization of artificial materials for investigation will be carried out by the project’s Strategy Board. Such prioritization will highlight the key emerging materials of concern from the environmental and human health perspective.
- As a follow-up step, we will engage with key **stakeholders**, including main EU regulatory bodies (ECHA, EFSA, and EEA) to understand their perspectives and key priorities and areas for improvement via direct communication and their published reports.
- Comprehensive review of **existing opinion papers and available reports** defining the key priority areas for artificial material research from the scientific community (e.g. [SAPEA](#) reports, that are part of the European Commission’s scientific advice mechanism).

- We will also **reach out to pertinent EU scientific projects** to address any knowledge gaps within the research area under study. The primary project objectives (i.e. innovativeness, goals and outcome) of investigated projects are outlined on the Funding & Tender EU portal.
- Based on the feedback from stakeholders and the scientific community, we will **delineate priority research areas and pre-select the relevant research infrastructure (RI)** portfolio relevant to the studied topic. Our specific focus will be identifying Research Infrastructures (RIs) with the capability to explicitly address the gaps and needs reported by the stakeholders.

Identification of relevant RIs

- This task will be done in close collaboration with ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures), specifically, the focus will be on implemented ESFRI RIs (referred as **ESFRI landmarks**), which need continuous upgrade to ensure the provision of state-of-the-art services. The emphasis is anticipated to be on established RIs within the domains:
 - **i)** Environment (8 RIs, of which we may consider EuroArgo, EMSO, LifeWatch).
 - **ii)** Health & Food (12 RIs, of which we may consider Elixir, Erinha, EMBRC, EU-OpenScreen).
 - **iii)** Physical Sciences & Engineering (13 RIs, a subset of which have instrumentation that is used for high-level analysis of artificial materials).
 - **iv)** Social and Cultural Innovation (5 RIs, of which SHARE, ESS or CESSDA may be of potential relevance for social sciences mapping of impacted communities).

In addition FHERITALE includes two ERICs: INSTRUCT and AnaEE.
- We will also investigate **ESFRI projects**, that are RIs in their preparation phase selected for excellence in science. They are included in the landscaping process due to their strategic significance for the ERA and to facilitate their realization. We pre-identified ESFRI projects in domains:
 - Environment (3 RIs),
 - Health and food (12 RIs),
 - Physical sciences and engineering (12 RIs).
- The landscaping will also reach out to the **ESFRI Forum**, which provides a platform for identifying strategic priorities for research infrastructure investment and development.
- In addition, we will investigate potential European RIs and networks (open to the EU scientific community) whose services and activities could be relevant for our identified priorities
- The outcome of this stage will be the “**First catalog of current state of services**” (milestone MS 3.1.)

3. Development of vision and Landscaping

- Based on the identified priorities and feedback from EU regulatory bodies (point 1), we develop a vision that will define the desired future state of the RI landscape, especially in view of upcoming political and scientific needs.
- The vision will be translated into specific questionnaires that will target the identified RIs from point 2.
- The questionnaire will be made in cooperation with both WP 3.1. and WP 4 to gather information on existing infrastructures and to identify points and areas for improvement.
- Initially, the specific interest will be to gather information on RIs condition, functionality, infrastructure components (including laboratories, equipment), human resources, and conditions to provide services.
- The questionnaires will be designed to collect also the RIs’ existing plans for development with identified priority areas.
- The outcome of this stage will be deliverable D3.2. **Cross-thematic landscape report.**

Figure: Overview of the landscaping strategy and associated milestones and deliverables.

4. Final Remarks

The presented landscaping procedure guidelines will be performed to identify gaps in existing RIs and prioritize areas where new or upgraded infrastructures are needed (task 4.2. Selection of key priorities, milestone MS 4.2.). The investigation of RIs will lead to strategies for technology development that may include upgrading outdated equipment or technology, novel software solutions for data management and analysis, training strategies for staff and scientists, or/and building new or upgrading existing facilities to address the priorities and ensure state-of-the-art RIs. In addition to scientific excellence, long-term sustainability will also be considered.

These landscape procedure guidelines will be shared with those sister projects that have either relation to similar ESFRI domains or that have indicated similar landscaping strategies.

Appendix

Acronyms

MPs	microplastics
NPs	nanoplastics
MNPs	micro and nanoplastics
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	The European Food Safety Authority
SAPEA	Science Advice for Policy by European Academies
EU	European Union
EEA	European Environment Agency
RI	research infrastructure
ERA	European Research Area

Outline of Questionnaire

1. Artificial material research

- What artificial materials are studied in RI, classification of materials (e.g., polymers, composites, ceramics, micro/nanomaterials)
- What properties of artificial materials are analyzed/ studied (e.g. biophysical properties, structure, composition, bioactivities,...)?
 - Characterization techniques utilized to analyze artificial materials to understand the properties and behaviour of the materials.
 - Use of computational modelling used to design or predict the properties of artificial materials
 - Details about the testing protocols or standards the RI follows
 - What artificial materials are sensed as key priority of artificial materials research?
- Target Applications: What are the intended applications for the artificial materials being studied (e.g., electronics, energy storage, medical devices)?
- Collaborations and Partnerships:
 - Collaboration with other institutions or industries on artificial materials research
 - Identified opportunities for new collaborations in this area?
- Challenges and Future Directions:
 - What are the main challenges faced in studying artificial material?

- o Are there specific research questions or areas of exploration in artificial material research?
- o What future directions do you see for research in this field?
- o Does RI intend to study smart materials (i.e. materials that respond to the environment)?

2. RI condition and infrastructure components

- Status and condition of infrastructure
- Details about the laboratories, their specialization, equipment/instruments, condition, and key pieces of equipment available in the research infrastructure for studying artificial materials.
- What research does the RI support? And limitations on the types of research?
- Data management, data storage, and computing facilities, policies and procedures for data security and access?
- Types of services provided?
- Strategy of quality assurance of the services

3. Future Trends and Innovations, development plans:

- What are the emerging trends in artificial materials research?
- Are there any breakthroughs or novel applications on the horizon?
- Recent upgrades, areas of improvement / major renovations of RI?
- Future plans to acquire new equipment or replace outdated equipment?
- Development plans for the RI- what are identified priority areas, and the rationale for the selection of these priorities?
- Strategy for sustainability

4. Human resources

- What personnel do you have currently available for service [1-..]? {provide list of type of personnel to chose from (e.g. lab technician, pHd, postdoc, data manager etc)}
- Describe the expertise field/skills for the position of {repeat the type of personell that was selected}
- What is the level of education for the position of {repeat the type of personell that was selected}, {provide list of types of levels of education to select from e.g. applied sciences, MSc, PhD, (junior, medior, senior staff)}
- Indicate the FTE available to support research requests for this infrastructure (available capacity) for the position of {repeat the type of personell what was chosen} to provide service {repeat service that was chosen}: {number 0.1-20 fte}
- Expertise the staff member cover? A number of key personals.
- Opportunities for staff development and training?
- HR challenges that limit functionality, e.g. insufficient staff to support the needs of researchers.

5. Conditions to provide services.

- Open access? -How accessible is the infrastructure to researchers and external users? Are there guidelines or protocols for accessing services?
- Who is eligible to use the research infrastructure (internal researchers, external collaborators)?
- What types of additional user support services are available (e.g., training, troubleshooting)?
- How can researchers access these services? What is the process for researchers to request access to the infrastructure and its services?

- Financial questions – e.g. Are there any fees associated with using the infrastructure?
 - Are there any limitations on how researchers can use the infrastructure?
6. Funding and Resources
- Sources of funding support of RI, e.g. resources for infrastructure maintenance and development
 - Concerns about funding stability or availability?
7. Strategy for innovation
- Areas of improvement and plans for their incorporation. Are there existing plans for enhancing or expanding the infrastructure?
 - Emerging technologies that are considered for future integration?
 - Strategy to stay updated on advancements in RI
 - How does the infrastructure align with broader EU research and innovation strategies?
 - What are the identified priority areas for improvement?